

SKATER Additive Learner (STAKERAL): A Data-driven Method for Delineating Covariate-specific Endogenous Spatial Regimes

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Summary

Understanding the heterogeneity of spatial processes is essential for spatial analysis, as existing methods are often limited in model complexity, flexibility and interpretability. In this paper, we proposed SKATER Additive Learner (SKATERAL), a method for delineating covariate-specific endogenous spatial regimes. SKATERAL extends the recently introduced SKATER regression framework by employing a back-fitting algorithm to optimise spatial regime delineation for each covariate. By modelling the spatial inequalities in self-rated health in Greater Manchester, we demonstrated the superiority of SKATERAL in multiple aspects, over two classic spatially varying coefficient models, Geographical Gaussian Process Generalised Additive Models and Multiscale Geographically Weighted Regression.

KEYWORDS: Spatial regimes, SKATER, Spatial process heterogeneity, Back-fitting algorithm

1 Introduction

Exploring the role of spatial processes and their multiscale heterogeneity is one of the fundamental foci of spatial analysis. Typically, spatially varying coefficient models (SVCs) such as Multiscale/Geographically Weighted Regressions (MGWR/GWR) and Generalised Additive Models with Geographical Gaussian Process (GGP-GAM) are considered as useful tools for revealing and measuring the underlying processes (Fotheringham et al., 2017; Comber et al., 2024). By locally calibrating or spline fitting on each observed location, continuous parameter surfaces can be estimated to represent the extreme heterogeneity of spatial processes. However, such approaches are often challenged by the risk of overfitting, severe multiple testing issues and the lack of interpretability of results (da Silva and Fotheringham, 2016). Alternatively, the discrete heterogeneity modelling strategy, exemplified by spatial regime models/spatially constrained clustered regressions (Spregimes)

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and multilevel models (MLM) with random effects, can largely mitigate the above issues. However, it requires a priori delineation of the spatial regimes/units (Anselin, 1988; Kreft and de Leeuw, 1998).

Recently, Anselin and Amaral (2024) suggested an intermediate data-driven solution, referred as SKATER regression, which can solve the regimes and coefficients jointly by using regression goodness-of-fit as the objective function of spatially constrained clustering algorithms. An example is the SKATER (Spatial 'K'luster Analysis by Tree Edge Removal) which was proposed by Assunção et al. (2006). This approach aims to identify multivariate discrete heterogeneity in spatial processes while remaining within the linear regression framework without permitting excessive degrees-of-freedom. Although this approach has demonstrated superiority among a range of clustering algorithms in regime delineation, its capacity as a SVC is still limited for two reasons. The first is that prior knowledge is needed to determine the number of regimes and the other is the fixed number and structure of regimes across each covariate which suboptimises the delineation and often results in biased understanding of the spatial processes.

SKATER Additive Learner (SKATERAL), a back-fitting spatial regime optimiser, is therefore proposed to extend spatial regime models to identify covariate-specific endogenous spatial regimes in this paper. We also compared it with conventional SVCs to demonstrate its usefulness as an alternative for modelling spatial processes, through an application on the determinants of self-rated health conditions in the Greater Manchester health region¹, England.

2 SKATER Additive Learner

A spatial regimes linear regression can be specified as:

$$y = \mathbf{Z}\boldsymbol{\beta} + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

where

$$\mathbf{Z} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}_1 & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{X}_2 & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \mathbf{X}_J \end{bmatrix}, \boldsymbol{\beta} = \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\beta}_1 \\ \boldsymbol{\beta}_2 \\ \vdots \\ \boldsymbol{\beta}_J \end{bmatrix}$$

with \mathbf{X}_j indicating the design matrix within regime j , $j = 1, \dots, J$ and $\boldsymbol{\beta}_j$ containing the coefficients for regime j . The spatially constrained endogenous regimes can be delineated with a heuristic approach operating in the same manner as SKATER, but optimising the Residual Sum of Squares (RSS) for each subtree after edge removal (instead of dissimilarity) as the pruning criterion for the Minimum spanning tree (MST) (for details, see Anselin and Amaral, 2024).

Based on the above notations, a linear regression with covariate-specific spatial regimes can be formulated as:

¹Here, the Greater Manchester health region refers to all the 10 Clinical Commissioning Groups overlapping with it, see details at Section 3.1

$$y = \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{Z}_k \boldsymbol{\beta}_k + \epsilon \quad (2)$$

where

$$\mathbf{Z}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{X}_{k,1} & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{X}_{k,2} & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} & \cdots & \mathbf{X}_{k,J_k} \end{bmatrix}, \boldsymbol{\beta}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \beta_{k,1} \\ \beta_{k,2} \\ \vdots \\ \beta_{k,J_k} \end{bmatrix}$$

with $\mathbf{X}_{k,j}$ and $\beta_{k,j}$ representing the design matrix and the coefficients for covariate k , $k = 0, 1, \dots, K$, within regime j , and J_k is the number of regimes for covariate k .

Inspired by the logic of Generalised Additive Model (GAM), a back-fitting algorithm, SKATER additive learner (SKATERAL) is introduced here to search the optimal covariate-specific regime delineation (Figure 1). To implement it, there is a need to set the criterion for determining the optimal number of regimes in a single SKATER regression: the degrees-of-freedom is reduced by $k + 1$ each time when a new regime is delineated, the best trade-off in this study is to minimise the Akaike Information Criterion corrected (AICc). Similar criterion such as Generalised Cross-Validation (GCV) and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) can also be employed, with the latter being particularly useful when pursuing sparse interpretations. The MST for each covariate can be built upon covariate-specific affinity matrices to allow more flexible regime delineation and account for attribute similarity while ensuring spatial contiguity. According to Fotheringham et al. (2017), the score of change in the residual sum of squares (SOC-RSS) $\leq 10^{-5}$ was set as the convergence criterion, but the calibration routines in practice can be terminated after achieving convergence for all the Z_k and the model can be straightly fitted within a linear regression framework. Thus, as with the SKATER regression, the availability of the classical Chow/Wald tests is preserved in the outputs of SKATERAL and the regime-wise estimates can be directly interpreted. This method has been achieved and wrapped in R.

3 A Preliminary Application on Health Inequalities in Greater Manchester health region

3.1 Data and variables

To demonstrate the validity of SKATERAL, we apply it to model inequalities in self-rated health conditions in the Greater Manchester health region and compare the results with two conventional approaches, GGP-GAM in R package `stgam` and MGWR in Python package `mgwr`, used to tackle heterogeneity in spatial processes (Comber et al., 2024; Oshan et al., 2019). In order to align with the National Health Services (NHS) catchment area, in this paper, the Greater Manchester health region is defined as the spatial concatenation of the coverage of the NHS Greater Manchester Integrated Care Board and the NHS Tameside and Glossop Clinical Commissioning Group. The

Figure 1: Diagram of the back-fitting estimator for SKATERAL

dependent variable is derived from the variable General Health of the UK 2021 Population Census² and is measured by the percentage of residents who rate themselves as ‘4 - Bad health’ and ‘5 - Very bad health’ in each Lower layer Super Output Area (LSOA)³. The preliminary independent variables include four widely recognised determinants of health selected from the demographic, socio-economic and environmental perspectives respectively: the percentage of older adults (PctOver65) and the percentage of whites (PctWhite) from the 2021 Census, as well as the 2019 income deprivation index (IncomeScore)⁴ and the index of air quality (AirQuality)⁵. All the variables were standardised to ensure comparability.

3.2 Results

The global model was well fitted based on the above variables and the effects of all the four independent variables were highly significant, suggesting a strong baseline for further local modelling (Table 1). Consistent with previous work, the percentage of older adults and income deprivation showed a significant positive relationship with the percentage of population in bad health. Air quality had a significant negative relationship with the percentage of people in bad health, with a less direct path to self-rated health than the first two variables. There was a positive association

²The General health variable is defined as a person’s assessment of the general state of their health, ranging from ‘1 - Very good health’ to ‘5 - Very bad health’ on a five-point ordinal scale. UK Census 2021 is available at <https://www.ons.gov.uk/census>.

³Lower layer Super Output Areas are the second-lowest level of geography for UK census statistics. They comprise between 400 and 1,200 households with a usual resident population of between 1,000 and 3,000.

⁴The income deprivation index measures the percentage of the population in an area who are out-of-work or are in work but with low earnings. The data is available at <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/english-indices-of-deprivation-2019>.

⁵The index of air quality was calculated from the inverse of Air Quality Domain score from the Access to Healthy Assets & Hazards (AHAH) version 3. The data is available at <https://data.cdrc.ac.uk/dataset/access-healthy-assets-hazards-ahah-previous-versions>.

between the percentage of whites and the percentage of population in bad health, whereas the relationship between race and health can be debatable.

Table 1: Global model (OLS) results

Variable	Est.	SE	t value	Pr(> t)	
Intercept	0.000	0.012	0.000	1	
Pct65over	0.382	0.016	23.179	<2e-16	***
IncomeScore	1.035	0.015	69.921	<2e-16	***
AirQuality	-0.077	0.014	-5.523	3.84e-08	***
PctWhite	0.228	0.016	14.594	<2e-16	***
N			1723		
R ²			0.746		

The covariate-specific Chow test results showed that SKATERAL can delineate spatial regimes more judiciously than SKATER regression which is optimal for 25 regimes (Table 2). For all the covariates, the normalised F-test of SKATERAL is larger, especially for its optimisation of the regime delineation of air quality.

Table 2: Chow test results for SKATER regression and SKATERAL

Variable	F _{SKATER-Reg}		F _{SKATERAL}	
Intercept	4.8761	***	8.2537	***
Pct65over	5.925	***	10.78	***
IncomeScore	5.2388	***	14.59	***
AirQuality	1.7674	*	6.6146	***
PctWhite	3.9441	***	5.7199	***

It is also interesting to compare the tuning parameters of SKATERAL with the conventional SVCs (Table 3). These parameters, smoothing parameter (SP) for GGP-GAM, bandwidth (BW) for MGWR, and the number of regimes (RG) for SKATERAL, characterise the complexity while calibrating the certain covariate. In this case, larger SPs, larger BWs, and smaller RGs represent less costly calibration. All the three models indicated that the calibration for income deprivation was the most complex among all the covariates. SKATERAL and MGWR both calibrated air quality with the lowest cost, while GGP-GAM used more degrees-of-freedom. The SP is the largest when calibrating the intercept for GGP-GAM. Similarly, MGWR employed a large bandwidth, while SKATERAL delineated a large number of regimes. A key reason is that, different from conventional SVCs, the size or structure of spatial regimes is not fixed, which implies that they can be well calibrated for large-scale processes while also taking potential localised effects into account.

For all the model diagnostic, SKATERAL demonstrated its advantages over the global OLS model as well as conventional SVCs (Table 4). Due to the tendency of using fewer degrees-of-freedom, SKATERAL may achieve a better fit by considering multiscale spatial processes for a single covariate, which suggests it as a useful alternative to the conventional SVCs.

Table 3: Tuning parameters for the SVCs

	$SP_{\text{GGP-GAM}}$	BW_{MGWR}	RG_{SKATERAL}
Intercept	8.58e-04	1114	22
Pct65over	1.03e-07	360	27
Incomescore	6.26e-09	43	28
AirQuality	1.21e-07	1722	5
PctWhite	2.75e-07	194	21

Table 4: Comparison of model diagnostics across the four models

	OLS	GGP-GAM	MGWR	SKATERAL
RSS	436.959	364.708	314.166	295.0743
R^2	0.746	0.788	0.818	0.829
Adjusted R^2	0.746	0.781	0.802	0.818
AICc	2537.786	2340.653	2260.572	2070.763

Overall, the local estimates surfaces were broadly similar over the three models (Figure 2). The results of paired Wald tests were also presented to demonstrate the statistical significance of the differences in the estimates of the regimes on either side of each regime border, allowing a post hoc re-delineation of the regimes in a stricter manner. The estimates surfaces for $\beta_{\text{PctOver65}}$ and $\beta_{\text{IncomeScore}}$ were highly consistent across the three models, indicating strong and globally significant positive associations. SKATERAL revealed more heterogenous effects for the intercept and the percentage of whites, including the localised negative association between the percentage of whites and bad health around Salford East and strong positive health effect for the omitted variables (β_0) in areas include Manchester City Centre and Media City UK. The negative association between air quality and bad health can be generally found by all the three models, while SKATERAL identified a regime with significant positive association in Leigh, which might be due to local misspecification and ecological fallacy.

4 Discussion

This paper proposed the SKATER Additive Learner (SKATERAL) approach, as an alternative to SVCs, for modelling spatial process heterogeneity. We also demonstrated its usefulness with a preliminary application on modelling spatial inequalities in self-rated health in Greater Manchester health region. Compared to other frameworks for modelling spatial process heterogeneity, it uses degrees-of-freedom more efficiently and can handle multiscale processes while mitigating potential overfitting and multiple testing issues (Table 5). SKATERAL is a flexible spatial regime optimiser that is model-agnostic and can be expanded from a linear regression framework to any model working on regression tasks, including machine learning and deep learning. However, similar to all the SVCs, SKATERAL is computationally intensive and could be challenged by the modifiable areal unit problem (MAUP) (Fotheringham and Wong, 1991). Furthermore, considering its graph-based and discrete nature, the sensitivity of SKATERAL to cross-validation and the convergence stability

Figure 2: Local estimates of SVCs (scaled by a covariate-specific max absolute scaler where $p \geq 0.05$ in grey), borders highlighted in black represent significant ($p < 0.05$) in paired Wald test

of its back-fitting estimator will be further examined in the future.

Table 5: Comparison of different frameworks for modelling spatial process heterogeneity

	Spregimes/MLM	SVCs	SKATER-reg	SKATERAL
Process representation	discrete	continuous	discrete	discrete
Knowledge reliance	knowledge-informed	data-driven	data-driven	data-driven
Multiscale flexibility	low	high	low	high
Degree-of-Freedom efficiency	high	low	high	high
Overfitting risk	low	med-high	med-low	med-low
Multiple testing issue	light	severe	light	light
Result interpretability	high	low	medium	medium
Computational cost	low	med-high	medium	med-high

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6 Biography

Sui Zhang is a second year PhD student in Planning and Environmental Management at the University of Manchester. His research interests mainly include spatially explicit methodological development and spatial inequalities in health.

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References

- Anselin, L. (1988). *Spatial Heterogeneity*, (pp. 119–136). Springer Netherlands: Dordrecht.
- Anselin, L. & Amaral, P. (2024). Endogenous spatial regimes. *Journal of Geographical Systems*, 26(2), 209–234, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10109-023-00411-2>.
- Assunção, R. M., Neves, M. C., Câmara, G., & Da Costa Freitas, C. (2006). Efficient regionalization techniques for socio-economic geographical units using minimum spanning trees. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 20(7), 797–811, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658810600665111>.
- Comber, A., Harris, P., & Brunson, C. (2024). Multiscale spatially varying coefficient modelling using a geographical gaussian process gam. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 38(1), 27–47, <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658816.2023.2270285>.
- da Silva, A. R. & Fotheringham, A. S. (2016). The multiple testing issue in geographically weighted regression. *Geographical Analysis*, 48(3), 233–247, <https://doi.org/10.1111/gean.12084>.
- Fotheringham, A. S. & Wong, D. W. S. (1991). The modifiable areal unit problem in multivariate statistical analysis. *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*, 23(7), 1025–1044, <https://doi.org/10.1068/a231025>.
- Fotheringham, A. S., Yang, W., & Kang, W. (2017). Multiscale geographically weighted regression (mgwr). *Annals of the American Association of Geographers*, 107(6), 1247–1265, <https://doi.org/10.1080/24694452.2017.1352480>.
- Kreft, I. & de Leeuw, J. (1998). *Varying and Random Coefficient Models*, (pp. 35–56). SAGE Publications, Ltd: London.

Oshan, T. M., Li, Z., Kang, W., Wolf, L. J., & Fotheringham, A. S. (2019). mgwr: A python implementation of multiscale geographically weighted regression for investigating process spatial heterogeneity and scale. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 8(6), 269, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi8060269>.